

Sultan Ibrahim Mosque in Rethymno

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This mosque was constructed inside the Rethymno Fortezza (hilltop fortress) after the Ottoman conquest of Rethymno in 1646. It sits over the previous site of the Venetian cathedral of San Nicolo. As of 1650, the vakf which supported the mosque included five villages in the prefectures of Malevyziou and Agios Vasileios Amariou, buildings in Rethymno, and the guards' dwellings in the fortress. In 1649, Mevlana Yusuf was assigned as the imam, and received a two-story residence near the mosque that was part of the vakf properties. The dome (14.50 m X 6.80 m) is made from limestone and sandstone, with interior square mosaic tesserae in brown and white. The mihrab, which retains original paint in green, yellow, red, and blue, has a plaque with part of an ayah (verse) from the Quran, referring to Zachariah visiting Mary in the Sanctuary ('kulllama dakhala 'alayha Zakariyya l-mih'raba', Quran 3:37). The rest of the ayah, not recorded in the inscription, narrates that Zakariyya found Mary with provision in the sanctuary, and asked her how it came to her; she replied that it came from God. Photographs from 1900-1910 show that the minaret was destroyed by that time. The mosque was restored in the 1970s and again in 1998-1999 and 2003-2005.

Date Range: 1646 CE - 1923 CE

Region: Sultan Ibrahim Mosque in Rethymno

Region tags: Greece

Sultan Ibrahim Mosque in the Fortezza of Rethymno, including the square mosque and the base of the minaret.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Giapitsoglou, Konstantinos. "Sultan Ibrahim Mosque," in *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*. Edited by Ersi Brouskari. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.
- Source 1: Zilli, Mehmed (Evlia). *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.
- Source 2: Zilli, Mehmed (Evlia). *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Edited by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, and Robert Dankoff. Vol. VIII. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2003.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://visit-rethymno.gr/rethymno/1_342

– Source 1 Description: Description of the mosque and further image gallery, compiled by the Municipality of Rethymno.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Mounded earth behind the walls of the fortezza

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: This mosque is within the fortezza walls.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: As the highest geographical point in the Old Town of Rethymno, the mosque is visible from a distance.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Notes: According to Evliya Celebi, earth was mounded behind the defensive walls of the Fortezza.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: This mosque is part of the Fortezza (fortified military base and living quarters for soldiers).

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Individual

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes

- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Other [specify]: Fell into disrepair

- ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - Other [specify]: N/A.

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once

- ↳ In modernity

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Supreme monotheistic God

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: Associated with Ottoman conquest of Rethymno

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: Associated with Ottoman conquest of Rethymno

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Marble

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Quranic calligraphy is carved in relief.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The mihrab is painted in multiple colors.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

Notes: The interior of the dome is tiled with square mosaic tesserae.

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: Quranic inscriptions

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:
– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.
– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme high god is worshipped, but is not considered to be physically manifested or present.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high god (monotheistic)

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 50-200

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Large scale rituals occurred twice annually; daily prayers occurred five times per day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Men

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Twice annually

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Non-muslim members of society may not have participated in the festivals

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-200

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: While feasting is part of the Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr celebrations, it is likely that the feasting did not take place at this location; however, other components of these festivals (for example, prayers) did take place at this location.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: A living space for the imam was originally located nearby.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The vakf supporting this mosque was likely intended to support maintenance.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned

with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - No
- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:
 - Yes
- ↳ Housed within the place/structure:
 - No
- ↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: A Quranic verse is inscribed above the mihrab.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sultan Ibrahim Mosque in Rethymno, Giapitsoglou, Konstantinos. "sultan Ibrahim Mosque," in Ottoman Architecture in Greece. Edited by Ersi Brouskari. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008. p.434-435

Reference: Sultan Ibrahim Mosque in Rethymno, Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.

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